

PROSPECTS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF POULTRY FEATHER WASTE INTO NATURAL DECOMPOSING PLASTIC AND FODDER

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Annotation: While the keratin contained in keratin is digested and digested. Ashkozone intestine tractate (keratin is the only enzyme bu keratinase. Animal keratin is necessary for the body to digest food, as well as for special cleaning. Iodine keratin is a molecular structuration polypeptide, a peptide and separately an amine acid.

Key words: molecular structuration polypeptide, a peptide, separately an amine acid, Animal keratin, leather, fur, wool, silk, cotton and the like, and various binding building materials: cement, lime, clay

INTRODUCTION

Throughout its life, mankind has used natural polymers much earlier. Natural polymers include those necessary for the preparation of clothing: leather, fur, wool, silk, cotton and the like, and various binding building materials: cement, lime, clay. Although the initial conditions for obtaining natural polymers were created much earlier, the production of chain polymers at the industrial level began from the beginning of the twentieth century.

In the first case, the production of polymers in tons on an industrial scale is based on cellulose. The physical modification of the initial polymer material was obtained in the middle of cellulose-cellulose-Hikhasr.

The production of a synthetic polymer began in 1906 after Leo Bakeland received a patent for Bakelite Tar, namely phenol and formaldehyde condensate material. Large-scale production of simple and complex cellulose polymers was established before and after World War II and continues until now.

What is polymer itself? Polymer (a word derived from grech, which means a lot and a piece, made up of many pieces). Polymers are inorganic and organic, amorphous and crystalline substances composed of mono rings, with long macromolecular chemical or coordination bonds. Polymers are high-molecule compounds. The amount of mono rings in the polymer (degree of polymerization) will be large enough. Polymers are substances whose molecular mass ranges from a few thousand to several million [1].

One of the most typical and commonly used representatives of polymers is polyethylene and polypropylene.

The consumption of polypropylene in Russia increased by 250,000 tons in 2002 to 880,000 tons in 2012[2], which is a very low figure, accounting for 1.6% of

polypropylene used worldwide and corresponding to 6kg per capita per year[3], in Western Europe this figure is 18 kg, in the United States it is 17 kg and in China it is 12 kg per The world's excess production of polypropylene is observed, while the excess polypropylene produced is around tons per year[2], with production capacity estimated as expected in 2015 being tons[3].

Thus, an excessive increase in plastic waste poses a risk to environmental sustainability. Is there a solution to these problems?

One solution to these problems is the creation of biodegradable plastics. It is worth noting that these plastics are also developed from waste. Bird feathers have a microcrystalline appearance and are highly resistant to mechanical as well as thermal effects at the expense of the keratin protein they contain. They are also solid from wood, and the strength value is equal to the value of polypropylene. 90% of the PAT is made up of a protein whose main component is beta - keratin, a protein with a fibrous, insoluble disulfide bond.

Keratin mainly: human and animal skin, similar to the substance of the branches of animals, is found on the outer layer - hair, claws, rhinoceros (nosorog) Horn, poultry feathers and beaks, etc.in the following structures. The new nomenclature of Keratin [5] basically this family also includes the epithelial cell cytoskeleton cell internal elements cytokeratin.

Figure.1. Microscopic image of intracellular keratin fiber

METHODS AND RESULTS

Keratins are divided into two groups:

- * α -keratin, which takes the form of a dense braid around the long axis of the molecule or is called α -Helix; these keratins form the basis mainly of hair (wool also includes), branches, nails and hooves of mammals.

- * β -keratin, which is much more rigid in shape with a zig-zag appearance, such as the polypeptide chain, is sometimes referred to as β lists; these keratins are

found in their tangents, chutes (e.g., turtle) on reptile animals, in bird beaks and feathers, in the nines of the gazelles.

In the United States of America, three billion pounds (1.4 billion kilograms) of poultry feathers are plucked per year, a huge part of the feathers go to landfills. At the next time, new technologies for processing poultry feathers were created by scientists, as a result of which the acquisition of environmentally friendly plasmas was achieved. But while this technology has not yet become public, the future will form the basis for the creation of environmentally friendly biodecomposing plastics.

The consistency of these plastics does not lag behind the consistency of wool, hair, nails and hooves.

The product from the bird's feather can be used as the desired item: a plastic cup (handle bowl) and plastic parts of furniture, and as arbors. One of the most fundamental achievements and advantages is this thermoplastic, biodegradable. As mentioned above, plastics are practically everywhere, in all areas: computer, machines, household appliances, furniture, when wrapping items, put in bags, bags that are present in all areas. Their disposal is not sufficiently developed or expensive. Because of this, plastics are accumulating in the seas and oceans. From this, all-headed scientific research institutes are conducting research on these problems.

The widespread use of biodegradable ecological plastics obtained from poultry feathers would be a powerful impetus for the development of the poultry industry, while finding a solution to the problem of plastic recycling.

One of the reasons for the relevance of keratins obtained from a natural bird feather is the possibility of processing poultry feathers and par products and obtaining products.

In our republic, more than 72 million agricultural poultry are now bred and eggs and meat are produced from them for the needs of the population.

It is also possible to obtain a secondary product, poultry feathers and fairies from poultry. Currently, about 30,000 tons of poultry feathers and pari per year in the Republic are thrown away as waste without recycling.

As mentioned above, several studies have been carried out by scientists from the University of Nebraska, United States, on the processing of poultry feathers and fairies, with significant results.

Currently, the production of pet feed from poultry feathers, as well as an environmentally friendly biopolymer, has been established in the USA.

When feeding livestock, poultry and fish, the use of blood flour, meat bone meal, meat flour, bone meal is important, Rich in protein, calcium and phosphorus. In the preparation of fodder flours, mainly non-edible and residual secondary products are used, which remain in low-priced birdhouses and when slaughtering poultry.

Feed made from poultry flour, when feeding livestock, the inclusion of feed ration in the composition of the feed ration ensures that the ration is of full value.

Poultry feather flour can be prepared in 2 different ways.

method: chemistry

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An amino acid (amino carboxylic acid-AMC) is an organic acid, a molecule of zirconium acid forms a carboxyl and an amino group forming. Amines is a fundamental aluminum Boolean element: carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, as well as nitrogen, sometimes amino acid of the radical, both of which are studied [6].

Keratin is (hydrolysis)yes, acid and alkalirequires this.

CONCLUSION

Summing up the above, it can be said that if it were possible to find an environmentally friendly solvent for keratins and obtain natural plastics from them, would have made a significant contribution to the developing economy of our republic. On the other hand, how many new jobs will be created by the establishment of waste product recycling. The establishment of obtaining natural decomposing polymers would have found a solution to a global problem that would be made from polymers and would have been polluting the environment for centuries.

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